

EDUAR, Gilles; GUIMARÃES, Maria. **A história da terra 100 palavras** [History of the Earth in 100 words]. Illustrations Giles Eduar. São Paulo: Companhia das Letrinhas, 2018.

REVIEW¹

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The book brings an exciting adventure that explains how the Earth emerged in the universe; how people, plants, and animals appeared on Earth; and how the moon and the sun came into being. Its presentation of informative texts, keywords, and illustrations of 100 creatures that have shaped history and evolution as a whole, as well as the inclusion of a timeline and a detailed glossary, makes it a rich addition to the reference section of any library. Author and illustrator Gilles Eduar defines it as a “documentary book”, from the French *livre documentaire*, known in Brazil as an “informative book”. Biologist Maria Guimarães and researcher of informative and infographic books Ana Paula Campos also collaborated on the project.

Keywords: Evolution. Universe. Story.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2019 Bologna. Books published in 2018 and reviewed in 2019. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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